

Direct and Indirect Titrimetric Determinations of Thiocyanate Ion in Metal Salts and Complexes using Lead Tetraacetate

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A simple but rapid and accurate method of determining thiocyanate ion in metal salts and complexes by a direct titration with lead tetraacetate in presence of sodium acetate and KBr has been developed. The direct titration with a visual or potentiometric end point involves an eight electron change per thiocyanate ion. A back titration procedure in which thiocyanate ion in metal salts and complexes undergoes a six electron change in presence of sodium acetate has been reported. A method for estimating cyanide and thiocyanate ions in mixtures is also described. The proposed analytical methods are useful for a rapid estimation of thiocyanate ion in metal salts and complexes on a macroscale and also for computing the number of ligand molecules present in a thiocyanate complex.

RAPID analytical techniques are essential for estimating thiocyanates, as they find a number of industrial applications such as in photography, printing and dyeing textiles, in the manufacture of synthetic dyestuffs, other sulfocyanides, thioureas and mustard oil, in medicine and freezing mixtures and as a reagent in analytical chemistry. The methods reported so far include the use of hypohalite¹, bromine,² iodine,³ iodate,⁴ H₂O₂⁵ and chloramine-T⁶⁻¹⁰ which involve mostly back titration procedures.

Lead tetraacetate (LTA, or PbAc₄) is a versatile oxidant, commonly employed as a reagent in preparative organic chemistry. Its solution in glacial acetic acid is generally employed for oxidation purposes. The redox potential of Pb⁴⁺/Pb²⁺ is about 1.40 V in presence of perchloric acid and is about 1.30 V in presence of sodium acetate. The presence of water accelerates most of the oxidations carried out with LTA if the solution contains sodium acetate. An important advantage of using LTA is the rapid and quantitative oxidation of substrates in presence of sodium acetate and some of the analytical procedures are so sensitive that very small amounts of compounds can be estimated accurately.

In the present investigations, we have critically examined the oxidation of thiocyanate ion in metal salts and complexes, by LTA. We have proposed (i) a rapid method for estimating thiocyanate ion by a direct titration with the oxidant in presence of KBr and sodium acetate, with a visual or potentiometric end point and (ii) a rapid back titration procedure in presence of sodium acetate. An eight electron and a six electron stoichiometry are observed in the two cases respectively. It was found that macro amounts of CNS⁻ ion can be estimated by a

proper adjustment of reaction conditions. Further, the method can be extended for estimating thiocyanate and cyanide ions in a mixture.

Materials and Methods

Triply distilled water was used in preparing the solutions. A. R. grade KCNS (E. Merck) was dried at 150° for two hours and its purity was checked.⁴ Metal thiocyanates NaCNS, Cd(CNS)₂, Zn(CNS)₂, Ni(CNS)₂·0.5 H₂O, Ba(CNS)₂·2H₂O, Pb(CNS)₂, UO₂(CNS)₂·3 H₂O and complexes K₄Pb(CNS)₆, KUO₂(CNS)₂·2H₂O, K₂Zn(CNS)₄·4H₂O, K₂Cd(CNS)₄·2H₂O and K₄Ni(CNS)₆·4H₂O were prepared by standard methods. The compounds were recrystallised from aqueous solution and their composition was checked by elemental analyses. Solutions of the compounds (~2mg/ml) in water or dilute acetic acid (only lead compounds) were prepared. Lead tetraacetate (Riedel) was used without further purification. An approximately decinormal solution of the compound in glacial acetic acid was prepared, standardised by the iodometric method and stored in an amber coloured bottle. All other materials and reagents were of accepted grades of purity. A Bajaj potentiometer with a platinum indicator electrode and a reference calomel electrode was used for potentiometric titrations.

I. Direct titration

Method 1

(a) *Visual end point*: A direct titration of thiocyanate solution with LTA was found practicable in presence of sodium acetate and KBr, the former to accelerate the decomposition of LTA. The oxidant liberates bromine from KBr, which in turn oxidizes

thiocyanate ion while at the same time serving as an indicator to detect the end point in an Andrews type of titration, employing carbon tetrachloride.

Recommended procedure : Take aliquots of thiocyanate solution in a 100 ml conical flask. Add 10 ml of 20% sodium acetate, 10 ml of 1 N KBr and 1 ml of CCl_4 and titrate against LTA with shaking till the appearance of a faint yellow colour in CCl_4 layer. Blank correction was found to be about 0.05 ml of 0.1N LTA.

(b) *Potentiometric end point :* A potentiometric titration of thiocyanate with LTA was possible in presence of sodium acetate (10 ml of 20% solution) and KBr (10 ml of 1N solution). A large potential jump of ~ 300 -500 mV was noticed for the addition of 0.1 ml of 0.1N oxidant at the equivalence point. In the absence of KBr, no potential break was found in most cases, while small potential jumps of the order of 100 mV occurred with a few thiocyanates, which however did not correspond to any definite stoichiometry.

Method 2

Blank correction and pipetting of the poisonous thiocyanate solutions can be avoided if the procedure of method 1 is reversed, by adding reductant to the oxidant. Volatility of bromine is the only source of error under these conditions, which however can be minimised by a proper choice of the titration assembly.

(a) *Visual end point :* Take aliquots of LTA solution in a 100 ml (two holed) stoppered conical flask. Add 10 ml of 20% sodium acetate, 10 ml of 1 N KBr and 1 ml of CCl_4 through a dropping funnel and titrate with thiocyanate solution with stirring slowly till the disappearance of bromine colour in CCl_4 layer.

(b) *Potentiometric end point :* A large potential jump of ~ 300 -500 mV was noticed for the addition of 0.1 ml of $\sim 0.03M$ reductant at the equivalence point in presence of 10 ml of 20% sodium acetate and 10 ml 1N KBr.

II. Back titration

In preliminary investigations, known amounts of thiocyanate solution were added to a known excessive volume of LTA in presence of sodium acetate in an iodine flask. The reaction mixture was set aside for various intervals of time at room temperature with occasional shaking. The excess LTA left unconsumed was iodometrically determined with standard thiosulphate. It was seen that stoichiometric oxidation of thiocyanate ion in the metal salts and complexes with a reproducible six electron change per thiocyanate ion took place in 5 minutes with a 40-50% excess of LTA. With a 10-20% excess the reaction is complete after 30 minutes.

Recommended procedure : Prepare a solution of salt or complex thiocyanate (~ 2 mg/ml) in water or dilute acetic acid. Add aliquots of the solution to a known excessive volume of 0.1N LTA (~ 40 -50% excess) in an iodine flask also containing 10 ml of 20% sodium acetate, shake the contents and set aside for 5 minutes. Add 10 ml each of 20% potassium iodide and titrate the liberated iodine against 0.1N sodium thiosulphate. Run a blank with LTA alone.

Results and Discussion

The eight electron stoichiometry found in direct titration procedures is indicated below, by assuming the in situ liberation of bromine from KBr by the oxidant.

Bromine cyanide formed could be quantitatively estimated by the iodometric method.¹¹

It is seen from equations (1) and (2) that stoichiometric quantities of KBr are required for a quantitative oxidation of thiocyanates.

The six electron stoichiometry observed for the oxidation of thiocyanate ion during the back titration procedure can be shown as follows :

The presence of CN^- in the reaction products was detected by spot tests.¹²

The results of analyses are shown in Table 1. It shows the range of amounts of thiocyanate employed and the percent error noted in the recovery. Each range covers the amounts present in 8-10 different aliquots of the compound. Further, as a comparison the results of analyses by the argentometric method¹³ are included in Table 1. It is seen that the maximum error encountered in the present method is about 0.5% while the silver nitrate method¹³ shows an error up to 1.2% in the estimation of complex thiocyanates.

Common anions such as sulphate, phosphate, nitrate, perchlorate and fluoride do not interfere, but cyanide and iodide ions interfere in direct titration and chloride and bromide ions in the back titration.

Estimation of thiocyanate and cyanide in a mixture :

The fact that cyanide ion does not interfere in the back titration method but is oxidised by LTA in

TABLE-1 TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF THIOCYANATES WITH LEAD TETRAACETATE

Compound	Range studied (mg)	LTA % error in recovery				AgNO ₃	Range studied (mg)	% error in recovery	
		Direct titration : Method 1						Visual end point	Potentiometric end point
		Visual end point	Potentiometric end point	Back titration					
KCNS	2.22-111.00	0.01-0.54	0.09-0.45	0.00-0.43	0.00-0.59	1.36-108.86	0.00-0.44	0.00-0.51	
NaCNS	1.88-112.69	0.00-0.32	0.00-0.54	0.00-0.27	0.00-0.27	1.71-102.55	0.00-0.58	0.00-0.58	
Cd(CNS) ₂	1.80-108.00	0.00-0.55	0.06-0.55	0.06-0.55	0.00-0.60	2.41- 96.32	0.02-0.42	0.17-0.42	
Ni(CNS) ₂ ·0.5H ₂ O	0.93- 92.75	0.00-0.54	0.00-0.54	0.00-0.54	0.00-0.39	2.53-126.60	0.09-0.40	0.00-0.39	
Pb(CNS) ₂	2.00-100.16	0.00-0.50	0.00-0.30	0.20-0.52	0.00-0.50	1.67-133.65	0.03-0.60	0.00-0.48	
Zn(CNS) ₂	1.56-124.74	0.00-0.51	0.00-0.26	0.00-0.32	0.00-0.58	1.88- 93.82	0.00-0.53	0.08-0.53	
Ba(CNS) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	1.00-100.00	0.00-0.35	0.00-0.35	0.00-0.50	0.00-0.60	1.01-101.36	0.00-0.49	0.00-0.49	
UO ₂ (CNS) ₂ ·3 H ₂ O	2.41-120.72	0.00-0.41	0.00-0.21	0.08-0.42	0.41-1.03	1.27-126.81	0.00-0.51	0.00-0.51	
K ₂ Zn(CNS) ₄ ·4H ₂ O	1.07-128.42	0.00-0.56	0.00-0.47	0.00-0.51	0.47-1.17	1.30-103.76	0.00-0.46	0.04-0.46	
K ₂ Cd(CNS) ₄ ·2H ₂ O	2.03-101.55	0.07-0.49	0.00-0.49	0.20-0.50	0.00-1.08	1.32-105.16	0.00-0.15	0.00-0.53	
K ₄ Ni(CNS) ₆ ·4H ₂ O	2.04-101.80	0.05-0.49	0.00-0.37	0.00-0.49	0.00-1.19	1.22- 97.60	0.00-0.29	0.00-0.29	
K ₂ UO ₂ (CNS) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	1.00-100.50	0.00-0.25	0.00-0.50	0.00-0.35	0.00-1.00	1.00- 99.70	0.00-0.50	0.00-0.50	
K ₄ Pb(CNS) ₆	2.03-101.35	0.00-0.52	0.18-0.50	0.00-0.50	0.28-0.74	2.73-109.36	0.07-0.37	0.00-0.37	

TABLE-2 TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF THIOCYANATE AND CYANIDE IONS IN A MIXTURE WITH LEAD TETRAACETATE

Amount taken	Visual end point				Amount taken	Potentiometric end point			
	CNS ⁻ (mg)		CN ⁻ (mg)			CNS ⁻ (mg)		CN ⁻ (mg)	
	Amount found	Amount taken	Amount found	Amount taken		Amount found	Amount taken	Amount found	Amount taken
0.85	0.85	1.13	1.12	0.84	0.84	1.12	1.12		
2.12	2.12	2.81	2.80	2.10	2.10	2.80	2.79		
4.20	4.22	5.60	5.60	4.24	4.23	5.65	5.63		
8.44	8.46	11.25	11.22	8.40	8.42	11.20	11.22		
16.80	16.88	22.40	22.47	16.88	16.87	22.50	22.54		
33.68	33.76	44.90	44.94	33.76	33.84	45.00	44.81		
67.52	67.59	90.00	89.76	67.56	67.68	89.80	89.62		
84.45	84.50	112.60	112.16	84.53	84.43	112.70	112.29		

a direct titration in presence of KBr with a 2-electron change¹⁰ can be utilized for estimating thiocyanate and cyanide ions in a mixture. An aliquot of the LTA solution (V₁ ml) is directly titrated against CN⁻ and CNS⁻ ion mixture as in method 2 (V ml). Then the amount of thiocyanate ion in 'V' ml of the mixture is determined by back titration with LTA. Let the volume of LTA consumed by thiocyanate ion in 'V' ml of the mixture be V₂ ml. The amounts of thiocyanate ion (x mg) and cyanide ion (y mg) in the reaction mixture are given by

$$x = 9.68 N V_2 \text{ and}$$

$$y = 13 N (V_1 - \frac{2}{3} V_2)$$

where 'N' is the normality of LTA.

Some typical results of analyses are shown in Table 2.

It may be concluded that the proposed analytical techniques are useful for a computation of the number of ligand molecules present in a thiocyanate complex and for estimating cyanide and thiocyanate ions in mixtures.

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